

Marina Colasanti: an all-blue Brazilian idea

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Marina Colasanti was born in 1937, in Asmara, today the capital of Eritrea. She lived in Tripoli, Libya. With the beginning of the Second World War, moved to Italy, in 1948 to Rio de Janeiro and became to be a Brazilian family. The saga imposed by the Second World War brought her literature as a companion. At just over six years old, she had already read some fairy tales and Pinocchio, her parents gave her a collection of classic literature adapted for young people as a gift. And also, Don Quixote and Sancho Panza, Ulysses, Marco Polo, The Trojan Horse, among many others, arrived.

In Brazil, she grew up and graduated from the “National School of Fine Arts”, specializing in engraving, but it was in journalism that he became famous. She was a reporter and then a writer and columnist for the culture section of *Jornal do Brasil* (the most influential newspaper in Brazil at the time). Still at *Jornal do Brasil*, she edited a children's supplement that took her into the world of children's literature and that would result in her first book of fairy tales. She translated countless authors from various languages: Jerzy Kosinski Giovanni Papini, Alberto Moravia, Iasunari Kawabata, Roland Barthes, Tommasi di Lampedusa, and finally reaching children's literature, with Collodi.

She has worked for numerous magazines, advertising agencies and on television as a presenter and interviewer. But it was as the behavior editor of a women's magazine that she became a pioneer in the discussion of gender issues in Brazil. Colasanti was essential in establishing a new feminine profile in the consciousness of Brazilian women. This work earned her three journalistic awards and four books and placed her on the national and international stage of the fight for women's rights: *United States Women's Studies Center* (1981); *Juror for the Prémio de las Américas* (Cuba, 1982); *Member of the National Council for Women's Rights* (1985).

Marina Colasanti has a unique versatility, communicating directly with women with journalistic essays that discuss the difficulties they face in society, talking about them and with them. At this time, she released *The New Woman* (1980) and *Woman from Here Forward* (1981). She became a multifaceted writer with a trajectory marked by diversity and intertextuality and

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entered the contemporary Brazilian cultural scene as a journalist, essayist, poet, chronicler, visual artist and one of the main authors who enchant children and adults with her fairy tales or ‘wonderful’ stories with original and innovative features. When writing her tales, she tells stories of kings, queens, shepherds, unicorns, carefully choosing the words, with her own magic that gives her narratives a poetic atmosphere.

Traditional tales are reinvented with a lyrical and sensitive tone, without interference from reason, as she herself explains, an exercise in introspection. Marina excels in maintaining the charm of mystery in her stories, she lives history inside out, a singular gift for reinventing traditional fairy tale narratives. We can say that her work has unique characteristics, as presented by Tietzmann (2009): transcontextualized contexts; her narratives do not begin with the traditional ‘Once Upon a Time’; the hero does not face difficult situations to overcome to get married or save the woman he loves; the past is imprecise and universal, valid for all times; o uses of the marvelous maintaining a dialogue with classic tales.

Her style is careful and woven with a symbolic language capable of providing different levels of reading according to each reader's experience of the world. The fantastic elements are interspersed in the narrative, promoting the unexpected between the lines of the text and the development of the reader's imagination and sensitivity. Thus, she reviews reality through fantastic narrative.

In addition to the texts produced, Marina Colasanti has always been available to her readers: children, young people and adults; teachers, researchers and reading mediators. Constant presence at events focused on reading, books and the training of reading mediators, such as the “FNLIJ Bookfair for Children and Young People” and “Biennial Bookfair” in Brasil and Latin America. Its production is highly appreciated in Colombia, Mexico, Argentina, Chile, Uruguay, Costa Rica, Cuba, among other countries.

As an essayist, she focuses on themes that relate reading to the Brazilian educational process, highlighting the importance of literature in the education of children and young people. Her work constitutes an important and vast object of academic studies with the most varied themes:

- The female condition;
- Marina Colasanti's fiction and the reinterpretation of fairy tales;
- The representation of violence against women in some of Marina's stories;
- The representation of social actors and the image of women in the context of feminist discourse in stories by Marina Colasanti;
- Feminist in stories by Marina Colasanti;

- Untied women: masculine intertexts;
- Law and Literature: the construction of women's identity in Marina Colasanti;
- The representation of women in literature for children;
- The presence of myth in Marina Colasanti's fiction;
- The fairies spin the fatum: the wonderful narrative by Marina Colasanti;
- In the labyrinths of love by Marina Colasanti;
- In the fairy maze; the female character in children's literature by Marina Colasanti;
- Eros in the imagination of Marina Colasanti;
- The myth of love in Marina Colasanti; and
- The language of fairy tales in the work of Marina Colasanti.

Today, there are more than 50 books (poetry, fiction, essays) for adults and children, recognized by critics, deserving of several awards and analyzed in numerous academic theses.

Silvia Castrillon defines her as follows:

“Marina Colasanti's work is universal, timeless and free from market classifications, mandatory reading for any age group, economical in resources, direct, without superfluous siege. It is possible that this consistency is due to the integration of all the arts in her life. Her poetry and her painting, as well as texts aimed directly at adults and essays, these beautiful pieces of literature, foresee the textile, a web in which she even weaves her own story(...) Marina is a complete artist, it is part of some way of being in the world of a generation for which art is essential to life. A global woman, who expresses herself through her interest in worlds different from those of which she is a part. A woman who represents a passion for life, a way of living that is at risk of extinction” (Castrillon, 2019, 21).

And this is how she introduces herself:

“I am the result of the books I read. From the age when memory begins, they have always housed and fed me. And, through childhood and war and so many changes – countries, language and culture – they represented the thread of resistance that held the journey together. Today, when an adult tells me that they read me as a child, I thank life for allowing me to do for others what so many did for me” (Castrillon, 2019, 20).

Marina Colasanti's work have international recognition. In 1998, she participated, as a children's author, in the *Internationales Literaturfestival*, in Berlin and as a writer-in-residence in Austin, at the University of Texas. Still in 1998, in Paris, she participated in a round table with Professor Helene Cixous, talking about the Brazilian author Clarice Lispector.

In 2005, she joined the international group of poets who went to North and South Korea with the program “Achieving peace, poetry for world peace”. Still in 2005, he received the *Italian Ordine della stella della solidarietà* from the Italian government, for her contribution to the culture of that country. She participated twice in international meetings as a storyteller of her own work: at the *IX Festival Internacional del Cuento* (Los Silos, Tenerife), and at *Palavras Andarilhas* (Beja, Portugal). In 2010, in the reading program of the 3rd Master's degree in books and literature for children and young people, at the Open University of Barcelona. In 2012, the book *Con su voz de mujer* was distributed in the Medellin Colombia metro by the government program *Palabras Rodantes*.

Her work has been awarded since its first releases: In 1979, *Uma ideia todo azul* was awarded the FNLIJ Orígenes Lessa Prize, representing the best for young audiences. Also in this category, *A Espada e a Rosa* (1993) and *Ana Z., onde vai você?* (1994). From 2001, with the book *Penélope* sends regards she became *Hors-Concours* of the FNLIJ Prize, having already won three times in the same category. Thus, the author was awarded the FNLIJ Award with *Hors-Concours* distinction in 2002, 2008 and 2010. Still rescuing the award from the FNLIJ – Brazilian section of IBBY – Marina Colasanti also received the *Highly recommended* seal in the years 1983, 1989, 1990, 1991, 1998, 2010, 2013, 2014, 2019 and 2020.

She won the Jabuti Award seven times in several categories, the most traditional literary prize in Brazil, awarded by the “Brazilian Book Chamber” created in 1959, including short stories (*Eu não sei se devia*, 1997), poetry (*Passageira em trânsito*, 2010) and children’s (*Breve história de um pequeno amor*, 2014).

The author has received many other awards throughout her notable professional career: the “Brazilian Association of Art Critics”, the “Latin American Children's Story Competition”, promoted by FUNCEC/UNICEF, and the “Latin American Norma-Fundalectura Award”. In 2010, she received the honorable news of the inclusion of one of her books, by the Venezuelan Book Bank, *Ana Z., onde vai você?* on the list of 10 books that are worth reading for the Ibero-American Public and Honorable Mention for the SM Ibero-American Prize for children's and young people's literature.

In 2023, Marina Colasanti is the winner of the 2023 “Machado de Assis Award”, from the *Academia Brasileira de Letras* for her lifetime of work. For the president of ABL, Merval Pereira, the Machado de Assis award seeks to distinguish writers whose work is known to the public and critics. Marina's first book dates to 1968. Today there are more than fifty titles published in Brazil and abroad, including books of poetry, short stories, chronicles, books for children and young people and essays on the themes of literature, women, art, social problems

and love. Through literature, she had the opportunity to resume her activity as a visual artist, becoming her own illustrator.

Marina was nominated, in 1994, 2016, 2018, 2020, 2022 and 2024 by FNLIJ – Brazilian Section of IBBY, for the Hans Christian Andersen Award granted every two years by International Board on Books for Young People (IBBY, affiliated with UNESCO) for living writers and illustrators (categories). In 2024, Marina becomes a finalist in the writer category. The prize is awarded based on selection criteria that include aesthetic and literary qualities in writing and illustration, as well as the ability to see from the child's point of view to encourage curiosity and imagination. And Marina represents Brazil, weaving with her fantastic narrative the threads of literature for children and young people from all over the world.

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